

Imaging

Large hematomas secondary to an excessive oral anticoagulation in antiphospholipid syndrome

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Carta de Pesquisa

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Case 1 – A 39-year-old female patient with systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) and secondary antiphospholipid antibody syndrome (APS), characterized by a history of lower limb deep vein thrombosis (DVT), and the presence of lupus anticoagulant and anticardiolipin (aCL) 52GPL and 47GPL, on two separate occasions, separated by three months). She was under chronic use of warfarin 7.5 mg/day. Five days before the consultation, she fell from her height. She had a contusion on the left thigh (Figure 1a), which evolved immediately with an extensive hematoma in that region and collection between the subcutaneous and muscular planes (dimensions by ultrasound: 8.0x6.0x4.0 cm). On that occasion, the INR was 3.41. She was treated with a reduction of warfarin dose and local cold packs.

Case 2 – A 49-year-old female patient with SLE and secondary APS (DVT associated with persistent aCL), in chronic use of warfarin 7.5 mg/day. Six days before the consultation, she fell up from her height and had a facial contusion and hematoma formation (Figure 1b) without traumatic brain injury on computed tomography. At that time, INR was 3.10. She was treated with a reduction of warfarin dose and local cold packs.

These are two cases of patients with AFS with complications secondary to oral anticoagulation. Warfarin use has a bleeding risk of 2% at three months and 3% at 12 months [1]. Logically, a higher INR has an increased risk of bleeding at a rate of 10.5% versus 0.6% when the INR is at a lower intensity [2]. In both cases, warfarin was suspended for 48 hours (INR reduced to less than 2.0), subsequently replaced

by low molecular weight heparin in total dose, in addition to the placement of local ice in the first days, and subsequent reduction of warfarin dose for adequate INR control with a target between 2 and 3 [3,4].

References

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None

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Ethical statement

The author declares that he followed the World Medical Association Declaration of Helsinki in this study. Informed consent was obtained from the patient for publication of her cases. No image of her is used.

Contributor's statement

JFC: conception. Analysys, writing, submitting.
YS: data analysis, revision

Figures 1a and 1b. Patients are presenting extensive hematoma of the left thigh (1a) and facial contusion and hematoma formation (1b).

